

Na⁺/Ca⁺²-INDUCED STRESS MITIGATION BY BIO-ORGANIC TREATMENT IS A KEY FACTOR IN ORGANIC COTTON PRODUCTION IN SALT-AFFECTED SOILS

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One of the main abiotic pressures endangering global sustainable crop production is salinity stress. By 2050, it is anticipated that approximately half of all agricultural lands worldwide will be damaged by salinity [1]. The physiological, biochemical, and molecular characteristics of plants are adversely affected by salinity stress in a variety of ways, which decreases not only soil fertility but also crop productivity. Reduced nutrient mobilization, hormonal imbalance, the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), ionic toxicity, and osmotic stress are all contributing factors to poor plant development under salinity stress [2, 3]. Agricultural land becomes salinized primarily as a result of salt buildup in the soil, particularly sodium (Na⁺) and chloride (Cl⁻) ions [2, 4].

The research aimed to investigate the role of exopolysaccharide (EPS) of a diazotrophic bacterial strain *Azotobacter chroococcum* XH2018.

It is important to bear in mind that for evaluation of Na⁺ removal, it must be taken those amounts of EPS, which is formed in the presence of Na⁺ cations. *A. chroococcum* XH2018 was cultivated in the presence of different concentrations of NaCl, taken as a salinity model.

After the third day of cultivation of *A. chroococcum* XH2018 in 2% NaCl, the formed EPS removed 11740.752 mg/L Na⁺, whereas from 1.0% NaCl – 5624.52 mg/L Na⁺ (Table 1).

However, the Na⁺-binding-capacity of exocellular proteins of *A. chroococcum* XH2018 was lower than that of EPS. For instance, from 2% NaCl supplemented Ashby medium the exocellular proteins of the strain removed 7229.135 mg/L Na⁺ after the third day of cultivation, whereas from 1.0% NaCl – 3184.497 mg/L (Table 1). Na⁺-binding-capacity of EPS and exocellular proteins totaled 18969.887 mg/L (11740.752+7229.135) Na⁺ from 2% NaCl supplemented Ashby medium.

Increasing NaCl concentration, as expected, negatively affected the formation of soluble exocellular proteins (Table 2). Therefore, the Na⁺-binding-capacity of exocellular proteins was low.

Table 1. Na⁺-binding-capacity of biomaterials of *A. chroococcum* XH2018 in different NaCl concentrations

Samples*	Amount of removed Na ⁺ (mg/L)
AzEPS-BF1+AzPr1	7521.87
AzEPS-BF2+AzPr2	8809.017
AzEPS-BF3+AzPr3	13369.143
AzEPS-BF4+AzPr4	18969.887

*AzEPS-BF1, AzEPS-BF2, AzEPS-BF3, and AzEPS-BF4 are EPS of *A. chroococcum* XH2018, produced in different concentrations of NaCl, from 0 to 2%. AzPr1, AzPr2, AzPr3, and AzPr4 are the extracellular proteins of *A. chroococcum* XH2018, produced in different concentrations of NaCl, from 0 to 2%.

Table 2. Formation of exocellular proteins by *A. chroococcum* XH2018 in different NaCl concentrations

Samples*	Amount of exocellular proteins, µg/mg	NaCl concentration, (%)
AzPr1	428.5	0
AzPr2	218.1	0.5
AzPr3	184.3	1.0
AzPr4	161.3	1.5
AzPr5	158.7	2.0

*AzPr1, AzPr2, AzPr3, AzPr4, and AzPr5 are the exocellular proteins of *A. chroococcum* XH2018, produced in different concentrations of NaCl, from 0 to 2%.

It can be concluded that EPS of *A. chroococcum* XH2018 can be used as a salt-mitigating agent in the salt-affected soils.

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